

Programme Development and Evaluation in Counselling

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Introduction

Programme development and evaluation in counselling is a crucial area of study with far-reaching implications for the enhancement of mental health services and the well-being of individuals. Counselling services cater to a diverse range of clients with unique needs and challenges. The development of effective counselling programmes ensures that interventions are tailored to address the specific issues faced by various populations, such as individuals with different cultural backgrounds, age groups, or mental health conditions. By studying programme development, researchers can identify gaps in existing services and work towards creating more inclusive and responsive counselling programmes.

Programme development and evaluation play a crucial role in improving treatment outcomes. Through rigorous assessment and refinement of counselling interventions, researchers can identify evidence-based practices that yield positive results. This contributes to the overall effectiveness of counselling services, helping clients achieve better mental health outcomes and facilitating the continuous improvement of therapeutic approaches. The field of counselling is dynamic, with new

Received: 22 November 2023

Revised: 1 December 2023

Final Accepted 9 December 2023

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10318872>

challenges and issues emerging over time. The study of programme development allows counsellors to stay ahead of these challenges by creating innovative and adaptable interventions. This is particularly important in the context of evolving societal norms, technological advancements, and the changing landscape of mental health. A well-established programme development framework enables counselling professionals to respond proactively to emerging needs.

Programme evaluation serves as a quality assurance mechanism for counselling services. Through systematic assessments, counsellors can determine the effectiveness, efficiency, and relevance of counselling programmes. This ensures that resources are utilized optimally and that clients receive high-quality, evidence-based care. The continuous evaluation of counselling programmes contributes to maintaining standards and fostering a culture of excellence within the counselling profession. Research in programme development and evaluation provides valuable insights that can inform policy decisions and professional practices in the field of counselling. By generating evidence-based findings, counsellors contribute to the development of guidelines, standards, and ethical considerations that guide the delivery of counselling services. This, in turn, has a positive impact on the overall advancement and credibility of the counselling profession.

The study of programme development encourages collaboration and interdisciplinary approaches. Effective counselling programmes often involve input from psychologists, social workers, educators, and other professionals. By understanding the collaborative nature of programme development, researchers can explore interdisciplinary strategies that enrich the counselling field and promote holistic approaches to mental health. Programme development and evaluation create a culture of continuous improvement and innovation within the counselling profession. Through ongoing assessment and feedback, practitioners can adapt their approaches to align with the evolving needs of

Received: 22 November 2023

Revised: 1 December 2023

Final Accepted 9 December 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10318872>

clients. This not only fosters a culture of learning within the counselling community but also encourages the development of cutting-edge interventions that push the boundaries of what is achievable in mental health care.

Objectives of Establishing Guidance Programme

The National Policy on Education (Federal Ministry of Education FME, 2004) section 9, subsection 89(i) identified G and C as an educational service that will facilitate the implementation of educational policies, and at the same time aid the attainment of the policy goals as well as promote effectiveness of educational system. According to the policy document, the objectives of the school guidance and counselling programme include:

1. Providing information to school children about career prospects. Career simply refers to one's life's work. According to section 4 subsection 20(b) the secondary education shall offer diversified curriculum to cater for the differences in talents, opportunities and future roles. The policy document further provides that learners will be made to pursue academic or vocational disciplines depending on their innate potentials. School guidance programme is expected to identify the aptitude of the learners in order to channel them adequately into their area of proficiency.
2. For effective implementation of the educational policy school guidance programme should help to provide information on the cognitive and more importantly the affective and psychomotor component of learners' behaviour. According to Igbogbor (2006) there is a gap on the effectiveness of Nigerian education on the heart of the learners.

He posits that Nigeria education should be repositioned towards reconstruction of the Nigerian organism. School guidance programme is expected to provide services which will touch the heart of Nigerians. The guidance counsellor should be able to develop instruments that can evaluate the “heart” and “hand” of learners. This is supposed to compliment the teacher’s evaluation of the cognitive domain for total development of the learner.

3. School guidance programme is expected to play the role of rehabilitation. According to Gidado (2002), UBE is expected to provide opportunities for individuals who had withdrawn from the formal education system.

Thus, traders, craftsmen, technicians, drivers, even prostitutes motor-park and political touts are expected to be rehabilitated into the school system at all levels of education. School guidance programme is expected to have proper understanding of these categories of people and thus help them to adjust in the school system.

4. School guidance should seek to achieve equal opportunity by discovering learners’ difficulties and making for individual differences. The philosophy of Nigerian education as captioned in section 1, subsection 4(c) stipulates that there is need for equality of educational opportunities to all Nigerian children irrespective of any real or imagined disabilities, each according to his or her ability. School guidance and counsellor should help to implement the principles of individualized instruction among learners. This will greatly minimize dropout rates.

5. School guidance programme must maximize personality adjustment of learners. It should be recalled that secondary school pupils are between the age of 11 years and 18

years. This age bracket marks the beginning and the height of adolescence. A lot of personality maladjustment is evident in the life of the adolescent. This ranges from sex life and drug usage. It is the role of school guidance programme to monitor children at this age so as to properly address life pattern at this stage.

6. Guidance programmes are expected to address school-community life. The school counsellor plays a vital role in the school PTA programmes. The counsellor should initiate programmes that will bring parents to witness the activities of their children and wards. Programmes like open day, PTA meetings etc should be organized by the counsellor for the achievement of the goal of education.

Purpose of Evaluation in Guidance and Counselling

Why does a guidance counsellor need to carry out evaluation? Evaluation is a process of making informed decision concerning achievement of set objective. Guidance services like educational programmes have set goals which they want to achieve. The purpose of evaluation in guidance and counselling are discussed below:

1. To ascertain if the goal of guidance programme has been achieved. A guidance counsellor initiates a programme with some set objectives in mind. These objectives describe the kind of changes that he wants to achieve in the participant at the end of the programme. He uses the techniques of evaluation to ascertain if the goals he observes of the programme has been achieved.

2. The guidance counsellor uses evaluation for the improvement of guidance programme. In the process of implementation of a guidance programme the counsellor utilizes the techniques of formative evaluation to ensure unity in the functioning of the elements of the programme. In an orientation programme the counsellor should be concerned with the level of participation of the beneficiaries. So, he could ask questions, consider the volume of the public address system, watch the sitting arrangement to ensure full participation.

3. For accountability in guidance services. Often time guidance services and programmes are expensive to implement. Fund for such programme may be provided by the school management, community, Parent Teachers Association or government. Naturally, these funding agencies are interested in knowing the effect of the programme on the participants. They want to know whether the programme is worth the amount of money that they spent on it.

The counsellor uses the outcome of evaluation to convince them that the programme is worth it. These bodies may also engage a counsellor as an external evaluator to ascertain the worthwhileness of the money spent on a programme.

4. For placement of learners in programmes and vocation. The guidance counsellor utilizes the outcome of evaluation to place individuals in programme and vocations. Persons come into a programme with different abilities. Different vocations also require different abilities. Using evaluation techniques, the counsellor is able to know where an individual will fit in a programme. He also uses evaluation to guide the individual into careers and vocations.

5. Guidance and counsellor use evaluation for the prediction of client behaviour. A scholastic aptitude test is used to predict clients' ability to perform in academic programme. A vocational aptitude test is used to predict an to perform in a vocation. A counsellor can use test to predict who can be with training good soldier, policeman, security service agent.

Principles of Evaluation

Evaluation is not an all-corners business, neither is it carried out in a haphazard manner. In this section we shall consider some of the principles that guide evaluation. Note that some experts refer to these principles as criteria for evaluation e.g., Asher (1976).

1. **Ascertain the purpose of the evaluation process.** Evaluation could serve different purposes depending on the need of the user. Evaluation could be made to clarify the goal of the programme, to ascertain the suitability of the operations-actions or activities needed to achieve the set goals-or the output, the extent at which the beneficiaries have gained from the programme and the level at which decision will be based on the evaluation outcome. The purpose of evaluation influences the technique aid precision of data collected as well as the variety of techniques to be used in data collection.
2. **Ascertain the goal of the programme to be evaluated.** Every guidance programme has set goals or objectives that it is supposed to achieve. These objectives are the compelling force behind time and money spent on it. These goats will inform the kind of data and instruments to be used in aiming at decisions about the programme.

3. **Decide on the technique of data collection.** Evaluation as a scientific procedure involves collection and analysis of data for decision making. The evaluator must decide on the technique most suitable for the kind of data needed. Decision on the kind of data should be guided by knowledge of technique, cost, validity of data collected as well as its reliability.
4. **Principle of multiple technique in evaluation.** This means that more than one technique can be applied in the process of data collection. For instance, in one evaluation study, an evaluator can decide to use test, observation and self-report technique in data collection. An evaluation report mainly requires information on the level of cognitive, affective and psychomotor changes in individuals that are involved in a programme. Such report will involve multiple data collection technique.
5. **The principle of proper utilization of evaluation techniques.** This principle demands that an evaluator should be aware that there are problems inherent in any evaluation technique. Sources of such problems includes: Sampling error, problems that can affect reaction to the items in the instrument e.g., ambiguity, response set, liability to faking and uninformed guessing. A third source of problem is bias conclusion arising from evaluator's predilection. Problems that cannot be checked are reported as limitations in evaluation report.
6. The principle that evaluation is a means to an end, and not an end in itself. This principle demands that evaluation result must not arrive too late, but at a time it can help to move the programme forward. The result should be such that it can lend itself to interpretation by varying audiences.

The Nature of Decision Making in Evaluation of Guidance Programme

When we engage in the process of evaluation, we are ultimately involved in decision making. In evaluation of guidance programme three kinds of decision are involved. The first is the decision on the best alternative for achieving a set objective. The second is a decision that concerns the operation of the programme in terms of suitability of materials. The third is a decision on the causal effect of the programme on the beneficiaries. Austin and Panos (1971) reorganized two conditions that predicated educational decision Viz: some reorganized educational objectives and at least two alternative means for accomplishing these objectives.

These are two or more alternative approaches in achieving a set of guidance and counselling goals. Consider for example, a guidance counsellor who has the objective or goal of acquainting secondary school students with career information. He or she can achieve this either through a career conference or by taking them on excursion to a place where such career is in practice. Development of good study habit could be achieved by group or individual counselling approach.

The second level of decision has to do with those elements that will affect the smooth rolling of the wheel of the programme. He or she takes decision on what can increase or enhance interaction between the resource persons and the best way to motivate and reinforce participants to engage and complete the programme etc.

At the third level he takes decision on the effect at the programme on the beneficiaries. He or she wants to ascertain that the goals of the programme have been achieved, and if not, what could be responsible.

At any level what are the factors that affected decision following factors- relevance, cost and availability. Relevance has to do with how such decision is capable of achieving set objectives, how it fits the prevailing social and cultural milieu. A guidance counsellor must confirm literature that a chosen approach is capable of achieving he/her set goal. He must support his points with valid philosophical and psychological theoretical background. Methods which discriminate on the basis of gender, ethnic belonging, race etc. cannot be said to be relevant. Chosen method must rule out tendencies to indoctrinate as well as religious bias.

Decision in guidance and counselling programmes must be guided by cost. In this era of UBE which is free and compulsory the counsellor must be careful in deciding to levy students for a guidance programme. School authority and government may also be reluctant to fund guidance. Considering these issues, a counsellor must decide on programmes that are not financially expensive to get the co-operation of stakeholders.

Decision in guidance and counselling programmes must be guided by availability. This has to do with practical problem of implementation. Some programmes no matter how robust they may seem may not be practicable. This might be as a result of restriction placed by tradition, administration or legal consideration. Imagine a behaviour modification programme that involves making participants to live in the prison yard to enable them have an idea of what it takes to be in prison; or using guidance and counselling techniques to correct behaviour disorder that is “considered” to have spiritual undertone. These procedures do not seem to be practicable. Occur in a learner having gone through an educational programme. Objectives defined clearly help to shape and guide the instruction and evaluation processes.

Meaning of Educational Evaluation

In any goal seeking activity it is natural to pause and consider the extent at which the set goals are being achieved visa-vis the material input. For instance, when you set to make a dress, you have a style in mind. As you put things together to arrive at your proposed style sometimes you pause to assess or evaluate the extent to which you are meeting your proposed style. Evaluation is making value judgement about the worth of a set of data obtained in respect of an attribute. Such value judgements are made within some frame of reference such as norm or criterion.

On a wider perspective, evaluation could be regarded as the sum total processes involved in gathering qualitative or quantitative data and making value judgement about them. For example, evaluation could be the entire processes of constructing and validating an achievement test and using same to obtain data on the achievement of students and then judging whether the students are low or high achievers in the test. Seen from this perspective evaluation embraces measurement. This is what is implied when such terms as educational evaluation is used.

According to Asher (1976) educational is obtaining and using information for judging which alternative should be selected in making educational decision. This definition derives from innovative perspective. Perceived better alternative of achieving educational goals should be evaluated to see if they are worth the huge amount of financial investment in them. It is from this stand point that American congress insisted in an Act that evaluation procedures be adopted for every innovative programmes.

Bloom, Hastings and Madaus (1971) and Gronlund (1976) define education evaluation is the systematic process of determining the extent to which instructional objectives are being achieved by pupils. Being systematic evaluation, it involves controlled observation of pupils. It assumes that objectives have been previously determined.

Purpose of Evaluation

Evaluation plays important role in educational system. Some of these are presented below;

1. **It contributes to teaching learning process.** Teaching, learning and evaluation are interdependent. The teacher must prepare instructional objectives in terms of the kind of behaviour change he wants to harness in the learner. In so doing, he ascertains the needs of the learner and provides relevant instruction. He evaluates the learning outcomes and uses the evaluation outcome to adjust the other stages in the teaching and learning process.
2. **Evaluation is very vital in programme Instruction.** This is an instructional system in which learning is broken down into several steps, each step being made up of set objectives. Evaluation helps to ascertain if a given set of objectives have been achieved to enable progress be made.
3. **Evaluation allows for curriculum development.** In trying to achieve this it gathers information about the various aspects of the curriculum like the objective, content, process and output. Such data when analysed provide useful input for decision making.

4. Evaluation provides data for school accountability programmes. In this, decision about the learner's achievement is made based on the outcome of evaluation using such devices as test and observation schedules.

Types of Evaluation

Different types of evaluation are used in school or educational system. They include:

1. **Placement Evaluation:** This type of evaluation is carried out in order to place individuals into educational programmes. Examples include joint some aptitude test to place persons in vocation or career etc.
2. **Diagnostic Evaluation:** This type of evaluation is carried out to find out the problems or needs of programme. For instance, diagnostic evaluation is carried out to know the needs of Junior Secondary School one students. It is also used to identify the problem that confronts the implementation of a programme.
3. **Formative Evaluation** is used during the process of a programme implementation to know where the participants are not doing well in order to direct them adequately towards the objectives. When we ask questions during teaching and learning in order to improve the achievement of educational goals, we are using formative.
4. **Summative Evaluation** is one used at the end of the programme to determine how much we have achieved the objective of the programme. Examples are end of term examination, West African Examination Council GCE and SSCE.

Changing Role of Evaluation

Received: 22 November 2023

Revised: 1 December 2023

Final Accepted 9 December 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10318872>

Evaluation traditionally serves as procedure for making critical and often irreversible decisions about each student's worth and his future in the education system. Little concern is paid on the welfare of the learner by teachers and administrators. This is what was in operation before the advent of continuous assessment mode of evaluating learning outcome. Evaluation in

Principles of Educational Evaluation

Educational evaluation is obtaining and using information for judging which alternative should be selected in making an educational decision. Such decisions have far-reaching effect on learners, teachers, administrators and the society at large. This far-reaching effect demands that educational evaluation should be guided by principles that make for effectiveness. Existing literature presents these guides as principles (Gronlund, 1976) or Criteria (Asher, 1976): In either case, these principles or criteria provide yardstick that must be observed if an evaluation process must be credible and goal oriented. The principles of educational evaluation are discussed below.

1. Ascertain the goal of the programme to be evaluated.

Every evaluation procedure targets a programme. A programme can be unit of instruction, e.g., a lesson; an innovation such as a new programme that is aimed at reducing the spread of Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome; an intervention such as introduction of midday meals in primary schools; an extension of basic education period from six years to nine years; the introduction of Post University Matriculation Examination Screening etc. These programmes involve huge government financial expenditure.

Government and funding agencies have certain objectives in mind which they want to achieve using such programmes. The evaluator provides information that guides funding agencies in taking decisions concerning aspects of the programme that will enable it to achieve its objective. Thus, the first step an evaluator takes is to ascertain the goals or objectives of the programme. These goals will inform the kind of data and instruments to be used in arriving at decisions about the programme. Some literature refers to the goal of educational programme as outputs, criteria, outcomes, achievement and dependent variables (Austin and Panos, 1971).

Outcomes or goals are usually expressed at high levels of abstraction. E.g., the development of capacity for critical thinking (also sees NPE). Most educational programmes are designed to affect concrete and measurable aspects of behaviour. These include students' achievements, skills, aptitude, values, personality etc.

2. **Decision on Techniques of Data Collection:** Educational evaluation should be guided by a decision of techniques of data collection for the purpose of arriving at a decision. This must be preceded by a proper clarification of the goal or objective of the programme. Evaluation techniques are selected on the basis of how valid and reliable the data collected is in arriving at a decision alternative. Validity requires that the data collected should provide information that sustains the decision that is to be taken. Reliability demands that the data collected must be stable so that decision based on the data can be dependable. Guided by this principle an evaluator should know when a given technique should be used instead of another. Decision on technique should be guided by level of precision needed as well as the cost of collecting these data.

3. **The objective of evaluation process is another guiding principle in evaluation.** Evaluation could serve different purposes depending on the need of the user. Evaluation could be made to clarify the goal of the programme, to ascertain the suitability of the operations- actions or activities needed to achieve the set goals - or the output, the extent at which the beneficiaries have gained from the programme and the level at which decision will be based on the evaluation outcome. The objective of evaluation influences the technique and precision of data collected as well as the variety of techniques to be used in data collection.
4. **Principle of multiple techniques Evaluation:** The principle of multiple techniques in evaluation means that more than one technique can be applied in the process of data collection. For instance, in one evaluation study, an evaluator can decide to use test, observation and self-report technique in data collection such decision is anchored by the goal or objective of evaluation. An evaluation report may involve information on the level of cognitive, affective and psychomotor changes in individuals that are involved in a programme. Such report will, require the use of test technique, observation and self-report techniques for the purpose of data collection.
5. **The principle of proper utilization of evaluation techniques:** This principle demands that an evaluator should be aware that there are problems inherent in any evaluation technique. This is responsible for the strength and weaknesses of an evaluation technique. Sources of such weaknesses include; sampling error. This weakness arises from the fact that in behaviour measurement only a sample of the behaviour is measured. How much the sample is representative of the universe of behaviour is indicative of how much this error is taken care of. An adequate content and process sampling can help to minimize this weakness in the use

of technique. Another source of problem that can affect utilization of evaluation technique is the problem that can affect reaction to the items in the instrument. This including wording in terms of extent of ambiguity, response set, liability to faking and uninformed guessing. The third source of weakness is improper interpretation of evaluation results arising people from evaluator's predilection and bias. Some of these weaknesses can be checked in the process of data collection, while others may be stated as limitations.

6. **The principle that evaluation is a means to an end, and not an end in itself is an important principle in evaluation.** Awareness of this will remove the problems of wearying subjects with data collection that may not serve any end. Thus, an evaluator must have a proper focus of the end of his effort. This will guide every other step in the process of evaluation. Evaluation result must not arrive too late such that it cannot help in decisions that can help the programme. The result should be such that it can lend itself to interpretation by varying audiences.

Nature of Educational Decisions

Decision which is literally judgement concerning which way to go is often taken at a cross road. The teacher, school administrators and government are frequently faced with the task of taking decisions that will enhance the achievement of educational goals and objectives. According to Austin and Panos (1971) "the need for rendering an educational decision implies the existence of two fundamental conditions; some recognized educational objective or set of objectives and at least two alternative means for accomplishing these objectives". Page 733.

The teacher is faced with the decision of the best instructional materials to achieve his stated objectives. Such decision is influenced by relevance, cost and availability. The teacher is faced with decision of curriculum and curriculum organization, method of teaching etc which will likely optimize the achievement of educational or instructional objectives.

The school administrator is faced with the decision of how to utilize the school subvention either in physical development or procurement of science, home economics, books and other instructional materials for the school.

Government is also faced with the decision of which intervention programme that should be funded to achieve the national goals which are achievable using education as a tool. Each educational decision alternative is born out of the belief that there is a casual relationship between educational objective and particular means available for achieving it. In each case, the decision maker believes that there is a best alternative for achieving set goal or goals of education. There are different theories of decision making viz; Stochastic theory of decision making (Wald, 1947), game theory of decision making (Neumann and Morgenstern, 1947) and inductive logic theory of decision making (Carnap, 1950) (Students should read about them in some details)

Austin and Panos (1971) identified the following distinct components of an educational programme outputs, inputs and operations.

1. **Outputs:** Educational outputs refer to the ends or objectives of the educational programme. They can also be referred to as criteria, goals, outcomes, achievements and dependent variables examples of UBE, Adedu, Med,

2. **Inputs:** Educational inputs are talents, skills, aspirations, and other potentials for growth and learning that the student brings with him into the educational programme. They can also be referred to as pre-tests, selection criteria, control variables, antecedent variables, interacting variables, motivations and aptitudes. Inputs are the human raw materials with which the educational programme has to deal. Inputs include personal characteristics of the students, family and community, and culture. Inputs could vary according to educational programme inputs affect student ultimate goal achievement in programme as well as the environment of the school.
3. **Operations:** Educational operations refer to those characteristics of the educational programme that are capable of affecting the student outputs. They include environmental experiences, means, independent variables, educational interventions experimental treatments, learning experience, learning strategies, curriculum, teaching style, instructional techniques. They are the means for the achievement of educational outputs or ends.

Evaluation Models

Evaluation models are procedures that are followed in carrying out programme evaluation.

These are discussed below:

1. CIPP Model

CIPP is the acronym for Context, Input, Process, Product model of evaluation. This model is creditable to Stuffle Beam (1968). Context evaluation provides the broad basis for stating the

Received: 22 November 2023

Revised: 1 December 2023

Final Accepted 9 December 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10318872>

objectives of the evaluation and the surrounding conditions of a possible programme. Input evaluation provides the specific data and considerations for the assessment of staffing, time, budget requirements, procedural barriers, operationally stated objectives, and educational and administrative strategies prior to the start of an educational programme.

Process evaluation takes place during the implementation of an educational activity or programme. It is concerned with the actual implementation of the programme, its description, and the facilitating and impeding factors as the programme proceeds. Product evaluation is a concerned with the end result of the educational programme on the students or participants. In other words, it has to do with programme accomplishment.

2. The Discrepancy Evaluation Model

This model of evaluation is Credited to Previous (1971). It is the procedure whereby differences (discrepancies) between a standard of performance and the performance itself in an educational programme are found and corrected. Discrepancy analysis is very much process oriented but also is concerned ultimately with educational products. It is concerned with what should be produced as well as how the product is to be produced. The what and how are defined in terms of discrepancies between developed standards (bench mark) and actual performance in implementation. These standards (bench mark) are compared for discrepancies. There are five stages of evaluation:

1. Design
2. Installation
3. Process,

4. Product and
5. Cost

Any differences found at any of these stages in the evaluation are given to the programme staff by the administrator (or the evaluator) so that the staff has a sound basis to make programme changes. Stage one activities are programme design and redefinition much like context evaluation in the CIPP model. Stage two, installation, and stage three, process is concerned with the implementation and continuation of programme as it was designed. Stage four, product, uses traditional classical evaluation and applied education research procedures to determine where the programme processes and conceptualization indeed have produced the product or achieved the objectives of the programme stage five, cost, is concerned with cost and benefits of the programme.

3. The Accreditation Model

Accreditation model is the procedure followed by programme accrediting bodies to ensure that educational programmes are achieving the objectives which they are set to achieve. In countries like United States of America there are accrediting bodies which carry out this function. In Nigeria, bodies like National commission, for Colleges of Education, Nigerian University Commission, Ministries of Education carry out accreditation functions for colleges of education, universities, secondary/primary schools respectively.

The accreditation process usually involves the collection of descriptive information concerning institutional characteristics such as faculty student ratios, teaching loads, size of the library, physical plant, required and elective courses, available teaching facilities and equipment's inputs like JAMB

scores for students' school certificate results of students, percentage of student going on to graduate etc. These yardsticks are determined ahead of the accreditation process members of the accreditation team only give a description of facilities on ground students can also be interviewed to get information from them on the implementation of the programme. Through this method in Nigeria, many departments in Nigeria University have been denied accreditation because their programme failed to meet the minimum requirement.

Evaluation Design

Evaluation designs are methods applied in collecting data about inputs, operations and output of a programme with the hope of taking decisions that will guide improvement or modification of the educational programme. There are different a types of evaluation design viz; historical, descriptive and experimental, descriptive designs include survey, case study, correlational and causal comparative or ex-post (ex-post) facto design. Experimental design includes pure experimental design and quasi-experimental design.

Validity of Evaluation Design

Validity of evaluation design means that the method used in collecting data actually collected data that provide relevant information for decision making in respect of an educational programme.

Conclusion

The study of programme development and evaluation in counselling is integral to the advancement of the profession. It ensures that counselling services are responsive to diverse client

needs, enhances treatment outcomes, addresses emerging challenges, maintains quality standards, informs policy and practice, encourages collaboration, and fosters a culture of continuous improvement. As counselling continues to play a vital role in promoting mental health, investing in the systematic study of programme development and evaluation is essential for the ongoing success and relevance of counselling services.

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